

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE INTERFACIAL BONDING AT SOLID/MELT INTERFACES IN MULTIPHASE CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Solid-melt interface, Interfacial bonding, Thermoplastic composites, Flow analysis, Phase morphology

ABSTRACT

Phase morphology and bond strength at solid/melt interfaces between continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic laminates and over-injected thermoplastic phases were investigated, both theoretically and experimentally.

The obtained results indicated that the interface temperature plays a critical role in determining the quality of the resulting interface. This was in turn shown to be related to the thermal properties of the phases, in particular, thermal diffusivities. Interface temperature was analytically computed based on thermal properties of the laminate and the injected phases, as well as the melt temperature distribution mapped over the interfacial region using MoldFlow simulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Incorporation of continuous fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites in complex thermoplastic structures is a novel, effective approach to enhance the load bearing capacity of the thermoplastic parts, thereby, enhancing the application spectrum of these materials.

However, the so called “cold interfaces” typically formed during fusion bonding at solid/melt interfaces, during the fabrication process of these hybrid composites, pose significant challenges to exploiting the full potential of the constituent materials [1, 2]. Unlike melt/melt interfaces, the existence of a temperature gradient in conjunction with poor heat transfer rate at the solid/melt interfaces might lead to non-uniform interdiffusion and entanglement of polymer chains across the interface [2, 3]. This often results in low interfacial strengths. Thermodynamic compatibility of the melt and solid phases is another important factor, which affects the interface quality and hence the overall performance of the resulting part [4].

Optimizing processing parameters, proper selection of the thermoplastic phases, and use of phase compatibilizers, are amongst the most widely studied subjects in relation to improving the interfacial strength of multiphase TP materials with “cold interfaces” [4-10]. However, the available literature has scarce instances of studies on the interface characteristics of the multiphase TP composites based on continuous fibre reinforcements. The presence of continuous fibres in the solid substrate, can significantly affect thermal behaviour at the interface as well as the response of the composite part towards the stresses caused by differential shrinkage.

The present study aims to provide insights into the morphology and characteristics of the cold interfaces formed as a result of fusion bonding between solid/melt phases of engineering thermoplastics, including polyphenylene sulphide (PPS) and polyether ether ketone (PEEK). Different cases were investigated in which the resulting composite specimens were fabricated by injecting fibre reinforced or non-reinforced TP melt over the continuous carbon fibre reinforced TP substrate as solid phase, with similar or different type of

matrix. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and single lap-shear tests, together with microscopic analysis were employed to assess the quality of interface in each different case.

DISCUSSION

Preliminary investigations indicated that interface temperature during injection has a significant effect on the strength and morphology of the incipient solid/melt interfaces. Therefore, interface temperature in each case has been calculated analytically.

$$T_i = (T_1 b_1 + T_2 b_2) / (b_1 + b_2) \quad (1)$$

$$b_i = (\rho k C_p)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Where T_i is the interface temperature, T_1 and T_2 are the temperature of the laminate insert and the polymer melt, respectively, and b_1 and b_2 are the corresponding thermal effusivities of the insert and the melt. ρ , k , and C_p are density, thermal conductivity and heat capacity, respectively. Figure 1a shows the interface temperature for one of the studied systems, namely, 30 wt% carbon fibre (CF) filled PEEK over PPS CF laminate. The significant difference observed between the average and interface temperatures is caused primarily by the enhanced thermal conductivity of the melt phase. Melt temperature at the flow front was calculated using MoldFlow software (Fig. 1b). This was used to obtain the distribution of interface temperature over the interface area.

Figure 1: (a) Analytical calculation of the interface temperature at various insert temperatures for the PEEK(30wt% CF)/PPS laminate system at a melt temperature of 385°C. Melting point of PPS is indicated by the dotted red line; (b) temperature distribution at flow front.

When the interface temperature is above the melting point of the insert matrix (280 °C in this case), the injected phase is able to melt the solid surface of the insert. The interface formed in this case typically shows non-uniform phase interpenetrations as can be seen in Figure 2 (left). This was not the case when the interface temperatures is lower than the melting point of the laminate matrix, where cracks can readily form due to the differential shrinkage, and poor bonding (Fig. 2 (right)). These together with the results of the single-lap shear and mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness tests were in good agreement with the analytical predictions of the interface quality.

Figure 1: Solid/melt interfaces formed at the interface temperature above (left) and below (right) the melting point of the substrate matrix.

CONCLUSIONS

The quality of the bonds at cold (solid/melt) interfaces depends largely on the interface temperature. This is in turn related to the thermal properties of the phases including thermal conductivity and heat capacity. Interpenetration of the phases at the interface contributes significantly to the enhanced bond strength, the lack of which can encourage the formation of interfacial cracks due to differential shrinkage.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was conducted in collaboration with Denroy Plastics, Rockwell Collins, Datum Design, and CCP Grandsen as part of a NIACE research programme. The authors are grateful for the useful discussions and support provided by the representatives of the participating industries, namely Marcus McCay, Noel Bloomfield, Alberto Lario, Nigel Mckibbin, Peter Quigley, Michael Maguire, and Aaron Gillies.

Tool fabrication and injection experiments were carried out at Denroy Plastics. Their great support during the course of the project is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are also thankful to Tencate and Victrex for supplying the composite laminates.

The second author would also like to acknowledge the financial support of Bombardier and the Royal Academy of Engineering.

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